

Determine and optimize the behavior of shuttle systems

Shuttle systems

This article summarizes Thomas Kriehn's dissertation [1] and refers to [2]. Shuttle systems are automatic storage systems that use shuttle carriers and elevators to transport totes. The horizontal transport and storage of totes within the tiers is carried out by shuttle carriers. The vertical transport of totes or shuttle carriers is done elevators. As part of this work, an analytical model and a simulation model were created to determine the system behavior of two versions of shuttle systems; these are presented in Figure 1. Storage strategies were developed to optimize the system behavior. The optimization criterion is to maximize throughput.

Figure 1: Left aisle- and tier-captive shuttle system with two elevators per aisle, on each tier there is one buffer location for storage and one for retrieval, right tier-to-tier shuttle system, three-dimensional view, based on [3]

Storage strategies

Algorithms were developed for the storage strategies class-based storage, sequencing of retrieval requests and warehouse reorganization. The class-based storage strategy assigns totes and storage locations to zones based on access frequencies. The storage strategy sequencing of retrieval requests sorts the requests in which the waiting retrieval requests are processed. The storage strategy warehouse reorganization determines the totes to be relocated and their new storage locations.

The application of storage strategies leads to a reduction in the travel time of the transport and thus to an increase in the achievable throughput. Table 1 shows examples of storage strategies. The storage strategies developed were compared with the random storage strategy. This storage strategy selects a random free storage location for totes to be stored.

Table1: Storage strategies to increase throughput

Class-based storage	Sequencing of retrieval requests	Warehouse reorganization
<p>Totes needed for the next shuttle system work cycle are relocated during the previous rest period.</p>		

Modeling

The model was created analytically based on probability and queuing theory as well as using random generators in a suitable simulation software tool that enables visualization of the processes (AutoMOD, version 12.6.1). The model enables the individual parameterization of shuttle systems with a variety of input variables (warehouse configuration, aisle geometry, kinematics, tote structure, applicable storage strategies and request structure) and determine the output variables throughput, cycle time, waiting time, degree of utilization, queue length and request lead time.

What is new is the possibility of adjustable distribution of the probabilities for controlling the storage locations. Each storage location can be selected with an adjustable probability for storage and retrieval. For the storage strategies class-based storage and warehouse reorganization, the developed algorithms (evolutionary algorithms and algorithms based on logically justifiable knowledge, see application example in Figure 2) arrange the zone assignment based on the adjustable distribution mentioned, i. e. the zone boundaries are determined automatically with the aim of increasing throughput as much as possible.

Figure 2: Optimal zones, defined on the left by the a priori algorithm, on the right by the evolutionary algorithm

Results

It was shown that the achievable optimization potential of storage strategies depends on several input variables:

- As the number of tiers increases, the potential for increasing throughput increases, as the travel distance of the elevator can be reduced more with each additional tier.
- As the number of positions in the aisle increases, the potential for increasing throughput increases (assuming the shuttle carriers form the bottleneck), as the shuttle carrier travel distances are shortened.
- The faster the elevator acts (travel times and tote handling times), the lower the potential for increasing throughput.
- Low Storage ratio should be taken into account by arranging an “empty zone”.
- A significant increase in throughput is already possible with two zones. Further increasing the number of zones results in further throughput increases to a lesser extent (and requires more complex control for practical application).

When using the storage strategy class-based storage, throughput increases of up to 54% could be achieved, up to 25% using the storage strategy sequencing of retrieval requests and the throughput could be more than doubled using the storage strategy Warehouse reorganization [1, 4].

Summary and Outlook

In this work, models for determining and optimizing the system behavior were developed for two versions of shuttle systems (aisle- and tier-captive, aisle-captive). The developed storage strategies class-based storage, sequencing of retrieval requests and warehouse reorganization lead to an increase in throughput by reducing the travel times of the transportation. Studies made it possible to quantify the increase in throughput compared to the reference storage strategy random storage. Furthermore, the effects of the input variables on the optimization potential of the storage strategies could be shown.

The models can be used to gain further insights into the system behavior of shuttle systems. The parameterization of some of the models developed in this work is publicly accessible via a website as part of the “SmartShuttle” research project [5].

The models can be used for application and further development by scientists, planners, operators and manufacturers of shuttle systems. Operators of shuttle systems can determine the existing optimization potential of the shuttle system and use it by implementing the algorithms in the control system. This means that as throughput requirements increase, a cost-intensive investment in new components, e. g. an expansion of the existing shuttle system with a new corridor with elevators and shuttle carriers can be prevented or at least delayed. In the planning phase, the models can be used to select variants.

Literature

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